

ON DRUM PLAYING TECHNIQUE DETECTION IN POLYPHONIC MIXTURES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the problem of drum playing technique detection in polyphonic mixtures of music is addressed. We focus on the identification of 4 rudimentary techniques: strike, buzz roll, flam, and drag. The specifics and the challenges of this task are being discussed, and different sets of features are compared, including various features extracted from NMF-based activation functions, as well as baseline spectral features. We investigate the capabilities and limitations of the presented system in the case of real-world recordings and polyphonic mixtures. To design and evaluate the system, two datasets are introduced: a training dataset generated from individual drum hits, and additional annotations of the well-known ENST drum dataset minus one subset as test dataset. The results demonstrate issues with the traditionally used spectral features, and indicate the potential of using NMF activation functions for playing technique detection, however, the performance of polyphonic music still leaves room for future improvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Automatic Music Transcription (AMT), one of the most popular research topics in the Music Information Retrieval (MIR) community, is the process of transcribing the musical events in the audio signal into a notation such as MIDI or sheet music. In spite of being intensively studied, there still remain many unsolved problems and challenges in AMT [1]. One of the challenges is the extraction of additional information, such as dynamics, expressive notation and articulation, in order to produce a more complete description of the music performance.

For pitched instruments, most of the work in AMT mainly focuses on tasks such as melody extraction [3], chord estimation [10], and instrument recognition [8]. Few studies try to expand the scope to playing technique and expression detection for instruments such as electric guitar [5, 17] and violin [12]. Similarly, the main focus of AMT systems for percussive instruments has been put on recognizing the instrument types (e.g., HiHat (HH), Snare

Drum (SD), Bass Drum (BD)) and their corresponding onset times [2, 6, 14, 18, 20]. Studies on retrieving the playing techniques and expressions are relatively sparse.

Since playing technique is an important layer of a musical performance for its deep connection to the timbre and subtle expressions of an instrument, an automatic system that transcribes such techniques may provide insights into the performance and facilitate other research in MIR. In this paper, we present a system that aims to detect the drum playing techniques within polyphonic mixtures of music. The contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows: first, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to investigate the automatic detection of drum playing techniques in polyphonic mixtures of music. The results may support the future development of a complete drum transcription system. Second, a comparison between the commonly used timbre features and features based on activation functions of a Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) system are presented and discussed. The results reveal problems with using established timbre features. Third, two datasets for training and testing are introduced. The release of these datasets is intended to encourage future research in this field. The data may also be seen as a core compilation to be extended in the future.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: in Sect. 2, related work in drum playing technique detection is introduced. The details of the proposed system and the extracted features are described in Sect. 3, and the evaluation process, metrics, and the experiment results are shown in Sect. 4. Finally, the conclusion and future research directions are addressed in Sect. 5.

2. RELATED WORK

Percussive instruments, generating sounds through vibrations induced by strikes and other excitations, are among the oldest musical instruments [15]. While the basic gesture is generally simple, the generated sounds can be complex depending on where and how the instrument is being excited. In western popular music, a drum set, which contains multiple instruments such as SD, BD, HH, is one of the most commonly used percussion instruments. In general, every instrument in a drum set is excited using drum sticks. With good control of the drum sticks, variations in timbre can be created through different excitation methods and gestures [16]. These gestures, referred to as rudiments, are the foundations of many drum playing techniques. These

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rudiments can be categorized into four types:¹

1. Roll Rudiments: drum rolls created by single or multiple bounce strokes (Buzz Roll).
2. Paradiddle Rudiments: a mixture of alternative single and double strokes.
3. Flam Rudiments: drum hits with one preceding grace note.
4. Drag Rudiments: drum hits with two preceding grace notes created by double stroke.

There are also other playing techniques that are commonly used to create timbral variations in a drum set, such as *Brush*, *Cross Stick*, *Rim Shot*, etc. Most drum transcription systems, however, focus on single strikes instead of these playing techniques [2, 6, 14, 18, 20].

In an early attempt to retrieve percussion gestures from the audio signal, Tindale et al. investigated the timbral variations of the snare drum sounds induced by different excitations [19]. Three expert players were asked to play on different locations on the snare drums (center, halfway, edge, etc.) with different excitations (strike, rim shot, and brush), resulting in a dataset with 1260 individual samples. The classification results for this dataset based on standard spectral and temporal features (e.g., centroid, flux, MFCCs, etc.) and classifiers (e.g., k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM)) were reported, and an overall accuracy of around 90% was achieved. Since the dataset is relatively small, however, it is difficult to generalize the results to different scenarios.

Following the same direction, Prockup et al. further explored the discrepancy between more expressive gestures with a larger dataset that covers multiple drums of a standard drum set [13]. A dataset was created with combinations of different drums, stick heights, stroke intensities, strike positions and articulations. Using a machine learning based approach similar to [19], various features were extracted from the samples, and a SVM was trained to classify the sounds. An accuracy of over 95% was reported on multiple drums with a 4-class SVM and features such as MFCCs, Spectral features, and the proposed custom-designed features.

Both of the above mentioned studies showed promising results in classifying the isolated sounds, however, they were not evaluated with real-world drum recordings, and the applicability of these approaches for transcribing real-world drum recordings still needs to be tested. Additionally, the potential impact of polyphonic background music could be another concern with respect to these approaches.

Another way to retrieve more information from the drum performance is through the use of multi-modal data [9]. Hochenbaum and Kapur investigated the inclusion of drum hand recognition in the data by capturing microphone and accelerometer data simultaneously. Two performers were asked to play the snare drum with four different rudiments (namely single stroke roll, double stroke open roll, single

Figure 1. Block diagram of the proposed system (onset detection is bypassed in the current experiments)

paradiddle and double paradiddle). Standard spectral and temporal features (e.g., centroid, skewness, zero-crossing rate, etc.) were extracted from the audio and accelerometer data, and different classifiers were applied and compared. With a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), an accuracy of around 84% was achieved for a 2-class drum hand classification task. It cannot be ruled out that the extra requirement of attaching the sensors to the performers’ hands might alter the playing experience and result in deviations from the real playing gestures. Furthermore, this method does not allow the analysis of existing audio recordings.

In general, the above mentioned studies mainly focus on evaluating the discriminability of isolated samples. The evaluation on real-world drum recordings, i.e., recordings of a drummer continuously playing, is usually unavailable due to the lack of annotated datasets. In Table 1, different datasets for drum transcription are presented. It can be found that most of the datasets only contain annotations of playing techniques that are easily distinguishable from the normal strike (e.g., Cross Stick, Brush, Rim Shot). For playing techniques such as Flam, Drag and Buzz Roll, there are no datasets and annotations available.

3. METHOD

3.1 System Overview

The block diagram of the proposed system is shown in Figure 1. The system consists of two stages: training and testing. During the training stage, NMF activation functions (see Sect. 3.2.1) will first be extracted from the training data. Here, the training data only consists of audio clips with one-shot samples of different playing techniques. Next, features will be extracted from a short segment around the salient peak in the activation function (see Sect. 3.2.1). Finally, all of the features and their corresponding labels will be used to train a classifier. The classes we focus on in this paper are: Strike, Buzz Roll, Drag, Flam.

For the testing, a similar procedure is performed. When a longer drum recording is used as the testing data, an

¹ <http://vicfirth.com/40-essential-rudiments/> Last Access: 2016/3/16

Dataset	Annotated Techniques	Description	Total
Data in [15]	Strike, Rim Shot, Brush	1 drum (snare), 5 strike positions (from center to edge)	1264 clips
MDLib2.2 [16]	Strike, Rim Shot, Buzz Roll, Cross Stick	9 drums, 4 stick heights, 3 stroke intensities, 3 strike positions	10624 clips
IDMT-Drum [9]	Strike	3 drums (snare, bass and hihat), 3 drum kits (real, waveDrum, technoDrum)	560 clips
ENST Drum Minus One Subset [18]	Strike, Rim Shot, Brush, Cross Stick	13 drums, 3 drum kits played by 3 drummers	64 tracks

Table 1. An overview of publicly available datasets for drum transcription tasks

additional onset detection step is taken to narrow down the area of interest. Since the focus of this paper is on playing technique detection, the onset detection step is bypassed by adopting the annotated ground truth in order to simulate the best case scenario. Once the features have been extracted from the segments, the pre-trained classifier can be used to classify the playing technique in the recordings. More details will be given in the following sections.

3.2 Feature Extraction

3.2.1 Activation Functions (AF)

To detect drum playing technique in polyphonic music, a transcription method that is robust against the influence of background music is required. In this paper, we applied the drum transcription scheme as described in [20] for its adaptability to polyphonic mixtures of music. The flowchart of the process is shown in Fig. 2. This method decomposes the magnitude spectrogram of the complex mixtures with a fixed pre-trained drum dictionary and a randomly initialized dictionary for harmonic contents. Once the signal is decomposed, the activation function $h_i(n)$ of each individual drum can be extracted, in which n is the block index and $i = \{HH, SD, BD\}$ indicates the type of drum

All of the audio samples are mono with a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz. The Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) of is computed with a block size of 512 and a hop size of 128, and a Hann window is applied to each block. The harmonic rank r_h for the partially-fixed NMF is 50, and the drum dictionary is trained from the ENST drum dataset [7] with a total number of three templates (one template per drum). The resulting $h_i(n)$ is scaled to a range between 0 and 1 and smoothed using a median filter with an order of $p = 5$ samples. Since a template in the dictionary is intended to capture the activity of the same type of drum, the drum sounds with slightly different timbres will still result in similar $h_i(n)$. Therefore, the extracted activation function $h_i(n)$ can be considered as a timbre invariant transformation and is desirable for detecting the underlying techniques. Segments of these activation functions can be used directly as features or as the intermediate representation for the extraction of other features.

3.2.2 Activation Derived Features (ADF)

Once the activation functions $h_i(n)$ have been extracted from the audio data, various features can be derived for subsequent classification. The steps can be summarized as

Figure 2. Flowchart of the activation extraction process, see [20]

follows: first, for every given onset at index n_o , a 400 ms segment centered around $h_i(n_o)$ will be selected. Next, the segment is shifted to ensure the maximum value is positioned at the center. From this segment, we extract the distribution features, the Inter-Onset Interval (IOI) features, the peak features, and the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) features as described below:

1. **Distribution features**, $d = 5$: Spread, Skew, Crest, Centroid, and Flatness. These features are similar to the commonly used spectral features, which provide the general description of the pattern.
2. **IOI features**, $d = 2$: IOI mean, and IOI standard deviation. These features are simple statistics of the IOIs.
3. **Peak features**, $d = 8$: side peak to main peak ratio α_i , and side peak to main peak signed block index difference Δb_i $i = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. These features are designed to describe the details of the patterns. To compute the peak features, first we find the local maxima and sort them in descending order, then we calculate the ratio and index difference between the side peak and the main (largest) peak as features.
4. **DTW features**, $d = 4$: the cumulative cost of a DTW distance between the current and the 4 template activation functions. To compute the DTW features, a median activation template of each playing technique is trained from the training data, and the cumulative cost of every DTW template for the given segment can be calculated. The examples of the extracted DTW templates for each technique are shown in Fig. 3.

The resulting feature vector has a dimension $d = 19$.

Figure 3. Examples of the extracted and normalized activation functions of (top to bottom): Strike, Buzz Roll, Flam, Drag

Figure 4. Illustration of the parametric forms of (Left) Flam and (Right) Drag

3.2.3 *Timbre Features (TF)*

To compare the effectiveness of the activation based features, a small set of the commonly used timbre features as described in [11] is extracted as well. The extraction process is similar to Sect. 3.2.2, however, instead of using activation functions, the waveform of a given segment is used to derive the features. The features are:

1. **Spectral features**, $d = 3$: Centroid, Rolloff, Flux
2. **Temporal features**, $d = 1$: Zero crossing rate
3. **MFCCs**, $d = 13$: the first 13 MFCC coefficients

These features are computed block by block using the same parameters as described in Sect. 3.2.1. The resulting feature vectors are further aggregated into one single vector per segment by computing the mean and standard deviation of all the blocks. The final feature vector has a dimension $d = 34$.

3.3 **Dataset**

3.3.1 *Training Dataset*

In this paper, we focus on four different playing techniques (Strike, Flam, Drag, Buzz Roll) played on the snare drum. As can be seen in Table 1, only Strike and Buzz Roll can be found in some of these datasets. Therefore, we generated a dataset through mixing existing recordings from MDLib 2.2 [13]. Since both Flam and Drag consist of preceding

Techniques	Description	Total (#clips)
Strike	Snare excerpts from MDLib 2.2 [16]	576
Buzz Roll	Snare excerpts from MDLib 2.2 [16]	576
Flam	144 mono snare excerpts $\alpha = \{0.1:0.1:0.7\}$ $\Delta t = \{30:10:60\}$ (ms)	4032
Drag	144 mono snare excerpts $\alpha = \{0.15:0.1:0.55\}$ $\Delta t_1 = \{50:10:70\}$ (ms) $\Delta t_2 = \{45:10:75\}$ (ms)	8640

Table 2. An overview of the constructed dataset

grace notes with different velocity and timing, they can be modeled with a limited set of parameters as shown in Fig. 4. The triangles in the figure represent the basic waveform excited by normal strikes, and the Δt is the time difference between neighboring excitations. All the waveforms have been normalized to a maximum amplitude of -1 to 1, and the α is the amplitude ratio between the grace note and the strong note.

In order to have realistic parameter settings for Δt and α , we annotated demo videos from Vic Firth’s online lessons for both Flam² and Drag.³ The final parameter settings and the details of the constructed dataset are shown in Table 2. The parameters are based on the mean and standard deviation estimated from the videos. The resulting data contains all possible combinations of the parameters with the 144 mono snare Strike in the MDLib 2.2. However, to ensure the classifier is trained with uniformly distributed classes, only 576 randomly selected clips are used for Flam and Drag during the training.

3.3.2 *Test Dataset*

To evaluate the system for detecting the playing techniques in polyphonic mixtures of music, the tracks from the ENST drum dataset minus one subset [7] have been annotated. The ENST drum dataset contains various drum recordings from 3 drummers with 3 different drum kits. The minus one subset, specifically, consists of 64 tracks of drum recordings with individual channel, mix, and accompaniments available. Since the playing technique is related to the playing style of the drummer, only 30 out of 64 tracks contain such techniques on snare drum. These techniques are annotated using the snare channel of the recordings, and each technique is labeled with the starting time, duration, and the technique index. As a result, a total number of 182 events (Roll: 109, Flam: 26, Drag: 47) have been annotated, and each event has a length of approximately 250 to 400 ms. All of the above mentioned annotations are available online.⁴

4. **EVALUATION**

4.1 **Metrics**

For evaluating the accuracy on the testing data, we calculate the *micro-averaged accuracy* and the *macro-averaged accu-*

² <http://vicfirth.com/20-flam/> Last Access: 2016/03/16
³ <http://vicfirth.com/31-drag/> Last Access: 2016/03/16
⁴ <https://github.com/cwu307/DrumPtdataset>

Figure 5. Results of experiment 1 (left) and experiment 2 (right)

racy [21] to account for the unevenly distributed and sparse classes. The metrics are defined in the following equations:

$$\text{micro averaged} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K C_k}{\sum_{k=1}^K N_k} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{macro averaged} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{C_k}{N_k} \right) \quad (2)$$

in which K is the total number of classes, N_k is the total number of samples in class k , and C_k is the total number of correct samples in class k . These two metrics have different meanings: while each sample is weighted equally for the micro-averaged accuracy, the macro-averaged accuracy applies equal weight to each class, which gives a better overview of the performance by emphasizing the minority classes.

4.2 Experiment Setup

In this paper, three sets of experiments are conducted. The first experiment consists of running a 10-fold cross-validation on the training data, in the second experiment the test data is classified with an annotation-informed segmentation, and the third experiment classifies the test data without the annotation-informed segmentation. Different feature sets as described in Sect. 3.2, namely AF, ADF, and TF, are tested using a multi-class C-SVM with Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel. For the implementation, we used *libsvm* [4] in Matlab. All of the features are scaled to a range between 0 and 1 using the standard min-max scaling approach.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Experiment 1: Cross-Validation on Training Data

In Experiment 1, a 10-fold cross validation on the training data using different sets of features is performed. The results are shown in Fig. 5 (left). This experimental setup is chosen for its similarity to the approaches described in previous work [13, 19]. As expected, the features allow to reliably separate the classes with accuracies between 80.9–96.8% for the different feature sets. Since the training data contains 576 samples for all classes, the micro-averaged and macro-averaged accuracy are the same.

Figure 6. Results of experiment 3 without background music (left) and with background music (right)

4.3.2 Experiment 2: Annotation-Informed Testing

In Experiment 2, the same sets of features are extracted from the testing data for evaluation. Since the testing data is a completely different dataset with the real-world drum recordings, a verification of the feasibility of using the synthetic training data as well as the proposed feature representations is necessary. For this purpose, we simulate the best case scenario by using the snare channel as the input with an annotation-informed process for isolating the playing techniques. The resulting 182 segments are then classified using the trained SVM models from Experiment 1. With ADF, the best performance of 76.0 and 81.3% was achieved for macro and micro-averaged accuracy, respectively. This experiment serves as a sanity check to the presented scheme. Note that strikes are excluded in this experiment, therefore, the micro-averaged accuracy mainly reflects the accuracy of the majority class, which is Roll.

4.3.3 Experiment 3: Real-World Testing

Experiment 3 utilizes a more realistic setup and is our main experiment. Each onset is examined and classified without any prior knowledge about the segmentation. A fixed region around each onset is segmented and classified. As a result, a total number of 2943 onsets (including the previous mentioned 182 playing technique events and 2761 strikes) are evaluated. Since the timbre features do not show promising results in Experiment 2, they are excluded from this experiment. To investigate the influence of the background music, both the recordings of the snare channel and the complete polyphonic mixtures are tested. The results are shown in Fig. 6. Without the background music, the best macro-averaged accuracy is 64.6% using ADF, and the best micro-averaged accuracy is 78.0% using AF. With the background music, the best macro-averaged accuracy is 40.4% using ADF, and the best micro-averaged accuracy is 30.4% using AF.

4.4 Discussion

Based on the experiment results, the following observations can be made:

First, as can be seen in Fig. 5, the timbre features achieve the highest cross-validation accuracy in Experiment 1, which shows their effectiveness in differentiating

	Strike	Roll	Flam	Drag
Strike (2761)	28.9	38.8	5.7	26.6
Roll (109)	8.3	66.1	11.9	13.8
Flam (26)	3.8	53.8	19.2	23.1
Drag (47)	46.8	6.4	4.3	42.6

Table 3. Confusion matrix of Exp. 3 with music and AF (in %)

our classes. This observation echos the results from the related work, which demonstrate the usefulness of timbre features for distinguishing the different sounds. However, when these features are applied to classify a completely different dataset, they are unable to recognize the same pattern played with different drum sounds. As a result, the timbre features achieve the lowest macro-averaged accuracy in Experiment 2, and the micro-averaged accuracy approximates the Zero-R accuracy by always predicting the majority class. This result shows that timbre features might not be directly applicable to detecting the playing techniques in unknown recordings. The activation functions and activation derived features, on the other hand, are relatively stable and consistent between the micro and macro-averaged accuracy. This indicates a better performance for detecting the proposed playing techniques in the unseen dataset.

Second, in comparison with the AF, the ADF tends to achieve a higher macro-averaged accuracy than the activation functions among all experiment results. Furthermore, the ADF is more sensitive to different playing techniques, whereas the AF is more sensitive to strikes. These results indicate that the ADF is more capable of detecting the playing techniques. This tendency can also be seen in the confusion matrices in Tables 3 and 4, where the ADF performs better than the AF in Roll and Drag, and slightly worse in Flam. The AF generally achieves higher micro-averaged accuracy than the ADF. Since the distribution of the classes is skewed towards Strike in the testing data, the micro-averaged accuracy of the AF is largely increased by a higher rate of detecting strikes.

Third, according to the confusion matrices (Tables 3 and 4), Strike and Flam can be easily confused with Roll for both features in the context of polyphonic mixtures of music. One possible explanation is that, whenever the signal is not properly segmented, the activation function will contain overlapping activities from the previous or the next onset, which might result in leakage to the original activation and make it resemble a Roll. The strong skewness towards the preceding grace notes in the case of Drag makes it relatively easy to distinguish from Roll for both features.

Fourth, for both activation functions and activation derived features, the detection performance drops drastically in Experiment 3 with the presence of background music. The reason could be that with the background music, the extracted activation function becomes noisier due to the imperfect decomposition. Since the classification models are trained on the clean signals, they might be susceptible to these disturbance. As a result, the classifier might be tricked into classifying Strike as other playing techniques,

	Strike	Roll	Flam	Drag
Strike (2761)	5.8	62.9	3.8	27.6
Roll (109)	5.5	74.3	3.7	16.5
Flam (26)	0.0	61.5	11.5	26.9
Drag (47)	2.1	8.5	19.1	70.2

Table 4. Confusion matrix of Exp. 3 with music and ADF (in %)

decreasing the micro-averaged accuracy.

Note that the proposed method does not take into account the onset detection at this moment. By adding the onset detection process, the detection accuracy will be further reduced, which decreases the reliability of the approach.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a system for drum playing technique detection in polyphonic mixtures of music has been presented. To achieve this goal, two datasets have been generated for training and testing purposes. The experiment results indicate that the current method is able to detect the playing techniques from real-world drum recordings when the signal is relatively clean. However, low accuracy of the system in the presence of background music indicates that more sophisticated approaches should be applied in order to improve the detection of playing techniques in polyphonic mixtures of music.

Possible directions for the future work are: first, investigate different source separation algorithms as a pre-processing step in order to get a cleaner representation. The results of Experiments 2 and 3 show that a cleaner input representation improves both the micro and macro-averaged accuracy by more than 20%. Therefore, a good source separation method to isolate the snare drum sound could be beneficial. Common techniques such as HPSS and other approaches for source separation should be investigated.

Second, since the results in Experiment 3 implies that the system is susceptible to the disturbance from background music, a classification model trained on the slightly noisier data could expose the system to more variations of the activation functions and possibly increase the robustness against the presence of unwanted sounds. The influence of adding different levels of random noise while training could be evaluated.

Third, the current dataset offers only a limited number of samples for the evaluation of playing technique detection in polyphonic mixtures of music. Due to the sparse nature of these playing techniques, their occurrence in existing datasets is rare, making the annotation difficult. However, to arrive at a statistically more meaningful conclusion, additional data would be necessary.

Last but not least, different state-of-the-art classification methods, such as deep neural networks, could also be applied to this task in searching for a better solution.

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